
PryfynMeth Manual

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Abstract

Invertebrate methylation levels are greatly reduced compared to their mammalian counterparts. As a result it can be difficult to determine methylation levels from false positives, and overly stringent FDRs can result in close to no differential methylation. PryfynMeth is a combination of tools designed to help the analysis of insect methylation data. It takes aligned data from Whole Genome Bisulphite Sequencing (WGBS) or Nanopore Sequencing datasets, performs a binomial test to help establish methylated sites, and formats the data for downstream differential methylation analyses.

<https://github.com/C-L-Thomas/PryfynMeth>

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1 Introduction

Invertebrate methylation data is handled differently than mammalian methylation data because they possess low-methylation levels. As a consequence, false positive methylation calls can quickly accumulate. In addition, low coverage, noisy signal and weak methylation patterns contribute to falsely calling methylation. A binomial test can help filter out CpGs that appear methylated by chance due to model overconfidence or noise. This can also reduce the number of input sites for differential methylation analysis to improve the statistical power of the differential analysis. Reducing the number of tests (input sites / rows) lessens the penalty incurred by corrections for multiple comparisons, thereby increasing the chance of detecting truly differentially methylated sites. In insect species, where large portions of the genome are never methylated, a good way of doing this is by using a binomial test to determine whether the site is methylated to remove sites that are never methylated from the differential analysis. For example, in an example *Nasonia vitripennis* study, this can reduce the input sites from 33 million to 300,000.

Binomial tests are commonly used in insect methylation studies. However, slight variations to their pipelines can result in differences in the differential result. I wanted to develop a tool that would allow people to easily run many variations of the pipeline flow, so they could determine how each of these variants impact their results. The preprocessing steps are designed to get Nanopore and whole genome bisulphite sequencing files to the point where they are ready for a binomial test. In addition, there are some additional quirks to the different types of input files that need to be ironed out to (explained in the sections below).

PryfynMeth is a set of scripts that are designed to streamline the steps between methylation read alignment and differential methylation analysis in invertebrate systems. The main features of the PryfynMeth pipeline are to prepare the files for a binomial test, performing the binomial test, filtering the results based on coverage and methylation status, and getting the files into the correct format for differential methylation analysis.

PryfynMeth can handle output files from Nanopore's modkit tool, and the whole genome bisulphite aligner Bismark (both stranded and destrand).

Figure 1: PryfynMeth Workflow

1.1 Installation

Download the repository:

```
git clone https://github.com/C-L-Thomas/PryfynMeth.git
```

Install:

```
pip install .
```

Test the installation works with the following command:

```
python PryfynMeth/pryfynmeth/binomial.py \  
-meta PryfynMeth/test_data/binomial/metadata.txt \  
-platform illu \  
-i PryfynMeth/test_data/binomial/input_dir \  
-o test
```

1.2 Preprocessing

This pipeline can handle Nanopore stranded data, Whole Genome Bisulphite Sequencing Stranded data and Whole Genome Bisulphite Sequencing De-stranded. However, with each data type there is some preprocessing required to get the data ready for a binomial test. The `nanopore_preprocessing.py` and `bisulphite_preprocessing.py` commands do exactly this, whilst allowing the user to determine the number of input sites they desire (eg. whole genome, sites with coverage, or sites which have coverage in at least one sample).

1.3 Binomial Test

To determine whether an individual site is methylated in whole genome methylation sequencing, it's common practice to assess if the observed methylation level is significantly higher than what would be expected by chance. This is typically done by comparing the observed methylation proportion to a statistical threshold, often using a binomial test. In whole genome bisulphite sequencing and Nanopore sequencing, this threshold is determined by the percentage methylation found in lambda spiked DNA. To identify methylated sites, you can use the `binomial.py` command.

1.4 Filtering & Sorting

Once the binomial command has been performed, you can filter based on your desired coverage, and generate output folders which possess your full binomial results (with coverage applied), a folder of sites which are methylated for each site, and a folder for sites which will be filtered for sites which are methylated in at least one sample. We also add the option to revert the shared sites back to their pre coverage levels to prevent downstream methylation analyses from

being inflated (and artificially increasing the number of differentially methylated sites). An explanation of this revert function is below. This example has threshold set at 10:

Table 1: Comparison of results with default and `-revert` options

Input	Default	-revert
1 / 9 (fail FDR)	0/0	0/0
1 / 20 (fail FDR)	0/0	1/20
2 / 20 (pass FDR)	2/20	2/20

Whilst 1/20 vs 2/20 may not produce a differentially methylated site, 0/20 vs 2/20 may. The revert option would take the 0/0 site (which failed FDR) and revert it back to 2/20, making for more stringent differential methylation analysis.

1.5 Formatting for Differential Methylation

We have the `dss_prepare.py` command to make any of the output files from the filter step compatible with the DSS differential methylation tool. Further tools will be added in future.

1.6 Example Decision Tree

To illustrate how the decisions in the preprocessing and filtering steps can have an influence on the output number of differentially methylated sites, we use the example below comparing differential methylation in Nasonia.

Figure 2: Decisions

2 Nanopore Workflow

2.1 Generating methylBED Files

Nanopore sequencing allows you to distinguish between 5mC and 5hmC methylation. To generate the correct Nanopore file types, you first need to generate methylBED files (see example file). Firstly you will need to generate modBAM files, either by live calling (in which case you can skip straight to modkit), or by using dorado to call modBAMS from a folder of pod5 files:

```
dorado basecaller sup,5mCG_5hmCG ./ \
--reference ref.fa \
--kit-name SQK-NBD114-24 > calls_sup.bam
```

After generating these modBAM files, you will need to sort them:

```
samtools sort -o calls_sup_sorted.bam calls_sup.bam
```

And then if you are using a multiplexing kit, you will need to demultiplex:

```
dorado demux \
--output-dir \
--no-classify \
calls_sup_sorted.bam
```

From the output modBAM files, whether you live called or not, you will need to perform:

```
for file in $(ls *.bam)
do
  base=$(basename $file ".bam")
  modkit pileup \
  --ref /genomic.fa --cpg \
  --threads 16 \
  --prefix "$base" \
  # --combine-strands \ #remove this hash before this to make data
  unstranded
  "$file" "$base"_meth.bed
done
```

2.2 Preparing MethylBED Files

2.2.1 Nanopore Preprocessing

The PryfynMeth pipeline can handle Nanopore files that have been processed through the modkit basecaller. These output files will contain a mixture of hydroxymethylation and methylation calls, and will include only sites with coverage. Like whole-genome bisulphite sequencing, you can choose how to handle genomic CpGs:

- All genomic CpGs – ensures uniform multiple testing across samples.

-
- CpGs with coverage in more than one sample – reduces total tests, still equalizes FDR across samples.
 - CpGs with coverage per sample – allows maximum reduction in tests, but treats samples differently in FDR correction.

```
python pryfynmeth/nanopore_preprocessing.py -i Input/ -ref cpgs.bed -  
    reduce  
done
```

- -i — Input folder: BED output from modkit.
- -ref — Reference BED file (from modkit's motif command, see below).
- -reduce — Keeps the same number of rows across all samples, but removes sites that never have coverage.

If you wish to run samples and retain each sample's individual coverages, the modkit output beds already do this. So to split hydroxymethylation and methylation you only need to run:

```
python pryfynmeth/nanopore_preprocessing.py -i Input/  
done
```

If you wish to include all genomic sites or sites that have coverage in at least one sample, you will first need to create a reference bed file with all possible cpgs:

```
modkit motif bed reference.fasta CG 0 1> cg_motifs.bed
```

After creating this file, you can then run the following command to get files that span every CpG:

```
python pryfynmeth/nanopore_preprocessing.py -i Input/ -ref cg_motifs.bed
```

If instead you wish to only have CpGs that have coverage in at least one sample, run the following command:

```
python pryfynmeth/nanopore_preprocessing.py -i Input/ -ref cg_motifs.bed  
-reduce
```

Two output folders from nanopore_preprocessing.py are Methylation_Data and Hydroxymethylation_Data. From this point on you will need to treat hydroxymethylated and methylated data separately, and if you wish to examine both, you will need two separate pipelines for both.

2.3 Adjusting Positions

Once preprocessing is complete, you will need to use the `nanopore_adjust.py` command. For an unknown reason (I have contacted ONT), modkit files come out 1 position out of sync for + strand bases, and the start and end position is the wrong way around for - strand bases. The `nanopore_adjust.py` command fixes this before the binomial test:

```
python pryfynmeth/nanopore_adjust.py -i Preprocessing_Output/
```

- `-i` — Input folder (output from `NanoporePreprocessing`)

2.4 Binomial Test

To determine whether an individual site is methylated in whole genome methylation sequencing, it's common practice to assess if the observed methylation level is significantly higher than what would be expected by chance. This is typically done by comparing the observed methylation proportion to a statistical threshold, often using a binomial test. In whole genome bisulphite sequencing and Nanopore sequencing, this threshold is determined by the percentage methylation found in lambda spiked DNA. To identify methylated sites, you can use the `binomial.py` command. This is perhaps the most important part of this pipeline. This uses the same input command for all file types. The metadata false discovery rate (lambda) can be determined by aligning the reads to a lambda genome and determining the percentage of calls that are read as methylated.

```
python pryfynmeth/binomial.py -meta metadata.txt -platform nano -i
Input_dir -o Binomial_output
```

- `-meta` — An input metadata file that reads the fail rate of calling methylation. An example metadata file can be found [here](#)
- `-platform` — `nano` for Nanopore, `illu` for Illumina (WGBS)
- `-i` — Input file. This is created either from the Nanopore or Bisulphite pipelines outlined above
- `-o` — Output Directory to be created

2.5 Filtering

Once you have generated binomial results, you may wish to filter samples with low read count. The `filter.py` command does just that. By setting a threshold it will output three folders. The first will be a full list of your sites in your binomial test output, but with the values and statistics adjusted considering your filtering. The second will be a folder of each sample's methylated sites

(sites with FDR less than 0.05). The final, will scan each of your methylated site files, and will add genomic locations that have been excluded from other samples, making sure each sample has the same number of input site.

```
python pryfynmeth/filter.py -i Binomial_Results_Folder -f
output_adjusted_sites -m output_pass_binomial -s output_shared_sites
-threshold 10 -r reverted_folder
```

- -i An input folder which should be the output (-o) from the binomial step
- -f An output folder that will give a full list of sites, but with adjusted values. For example, if threshold is set at 10 and the site in question passes FDR but has fewer reads than 10, the reads, methylation count and non-methylation could will be set at 0, and the FDR will become 1 (failing).
- -m An output folder that subsets each input file to only give methylated sites (ie those with an FDR less than 0.05).
- -threshold Anything lower than the number set here will convert the methylation count, non-methylation count and coverage numbers to 0, making the FDR fail.
- -s An output folder that subsets the input files, so that only rows that are methylated in at least one sample are kept.
- -r This is an optional tag (but recommended). If included, sites which failed binomial but have over the threshold coverage will be reverted to their original input values. The logic for this is that by changing these values to 0, you may artificially be increasing the difference between samples and consequentially increase the number of differentially methylated sites. This example has threshold set at 10:

Table 2: Comparison of results with default and `-revert` options

Input	Default	-revert
1 / 9 (fail FDR)	0/0	0/0
1 / 20 (fail FDR)	0/0	1/20
2 / 20 (pass FDR)	2/20	2/20

I find it easiest to run all options (filtered, methylated, subset and revert), which allows you to inspect how many sites proceed for each option, before making a decision for the next step.

3 Stranded WGBS Workflow

3.1 Background

Whole genome bisulphite sequencing files are frequently generated with Illumina sequencing. The PryfynMeth pipeline can handle file types output from the Bismark Bisulfite Read Mapper and Methylation Caller pipeline. This section discusses stranded methylation data:

- Stranded data has the + and - strands as separate entities.
- Destranded data merges strands. For CpGs, destranding might be preferable, especially with low coverage.

Example: Stranded vs Destranded

Table 3: Example methylation entries

Chr	Start	Strand	Methylation Fraction	Type
Chr1	101	+	8/9	Stranded
Chr1	102	-	11/15	Stranded
Chr1	101	*	19/24	Destranded

If filtering on coverage (e.g., coverage ≥ 10), you may discard useful strand data (e.g., 8/9 becomes 0/0). Destranding helps preserve meaningful information in such cases. Stranded data can be generated using Bismark's `bismark_methylation_extractor` command in the pipeline illustrated below.

3.2 Generating Stranded Methylation Data

3.2.1 Alignment

```
Bismark-0.24.2/bismark \  
  --multicore 4 --genome dir_to_genome_files -1 {input.read1} -2 {  
  input.read2}
```

Be sure to also align to lambda to generate values for your metadata table.

3.2.2 Remove PCR duplicates

```
Bismark-0.24.2/deduplicate_bismark -p --bam {input}
```

3.2.3 Extract Methylation

```
Bismark-0.24.2/bismark_methylation_extractor \  
  --no_overlap --comprehensive --bedgraph --report --  
  cytosine_report \  
  --genome_folder dir_to_genome_files {input}
```

3.2.4 Generate Coverage File

```
Bismark-0.24.2/coverage2cytosine \  
  -o {params} \  
  --genome_folder dir_to_genome_files {input}
```

3.3 Stranded WGBS Preprocessing

From the output file ending in report from the Bismark pipeline, you can then perform the PryfynMeth Preprocessing step:

```
python pryfynmeth/bisulphite_preprocessing.py -i Input -o all_Input -type  
  stranded --output_type all, coverage or shared #OPTION_DEPENDENT:  
  template_cov_file.cov
```

- -i — Input folder: cov or report files.
- -o — Output folder: reformatted files to be used by binomial.py.
- -type — stranded or destrand.
- -output_type — One of: all, coverage, or shared.

To decide which command for `-output_type` is suitable for your analyses, see the section which describes this in the Home Wiki page. Below describes how you would use each option. The following will retain every row for stranded methylation data. This approach will ensure each sample is treated the same in FDR:

```
python pryfynmeth/bisulphite_preprocessing.py -i Input -o all_Input -type  
  stranded --output_type all
```

The following will retain every row that has coverage in at least 1 sample for stranded methylation data. This approach will ensure each sample is treated the same in FDR, but will minimise the number of rows (potentially not by much):

```
python pryfynmeth/bisulphite_preprocessing.py -i Input -o all_Input -type  
  stranded --output_type shared
```

3.4 Binomial Test

To determine whether an individual site is methylated in whole genome methylation sequencing, it's common practice to assess if the observed methylation level is significantly higher than what would be expected by chance. This is typically done by comparing the observed methylation proportion to a statistical threshold, often using a binomial test. In whole

genome bisulphite sequencing and Nanopore sequencing, this threshold is determined by the percentage methylation found in lambda spiked DNA. To identify methylated sites, you can use the `binomial.py` command.

This is perhaps the most important part of this pipeline. This uses the same input command for all file types. The metadata false discovery rate (lambda) can be determined by aligning the reads to a lambda genome and determining the percentage of calls that are read as methylated. Your input directory for stranded data are output files from `bismark_methylation_extractor` with the `-report` flag (ends in `*report.txt`).

```
python pryfynmeth/binomial.py -meta metadata.txt -platform illu -i
Input_dir -o Binomial_output
```

- `-meta` — An input metadata file that reads the fail rate of calling methylation. An example metadata file can be found [here](#)
- `-platform` — nano for Nanopore, illu for Illumina (WGBS)
- `-i` — Input file. This is created either from the Nanopore or Bisulphite pipelines outlined above
- `-o` — Output Directory to be created shared.

3.5 Filtering

Once you have generated binomial results, you may wish to filter samples with low read count. The `filter.py` command does just that. By setting a threshold it will output three folders. The first will be a full list of your sites in your binomial test output, but with the values and statistics adjusted considering your filtering. The second will be a folder of each sample's methylated sites (sites with FDR less than 0.05). The final, will scan each of your methylated site files, and will add genomic locations that have been excluded from other samples, making sure each sample has the same number of input site.

```
python pryfynmeth/filter.py -i Binomial_Results_Folder -f
output_adjusted_sites -m output_pass_binomial -s output_shared_sites
-threshold 10 -r reverted_folder
```

- `-i` An input folder which should be the output (`-o`) from the binomial step
- `-f` An output folder that will give a full list of sites, but with adjusted values. For example, if threshold is set at 10 and the site in question passes FDR but has fewer reads than 10, the reads, methylation count and non-methylation could will be set at 0, and the FDR will become 1 (failing).
- `-m` An output folder that subsets each input file to only give methylated sites (ie those with an FDR less than 0.05).

-
- -threshold Anything lower than the number set here will convert the methylation count, non-methylation count and coverage numbers to 0, making the FDR fail.
 - -s An output folder that subsets the input files, so that only rows that are methylated in at least one sample are kept.
 - -r This is an optional tag (but recommended). If included, sites which failed binomial but have over the threshold coverage will be reverted to their original input values. The logic for this is that by changing these values to 0, you may artificially be increasing the difference between samples and consequentially increase the number of differentially methylated sites. This example has threshold set at 10:

Table 4: Comparison of results with default and `-revert` options

Input	Default	-revert
1 / 9 (fail FDR)	0/0	0/0
1 / 20 (fail FDR)	0/0	1/20
2 / 20 (pass FDR)	2/20	2/20

I find it easiest to run all options (filtered, methylated, subset and revert), which allows you to inspect how many sites proceed for each option, before making a decision for the next step.

4 Destranded WGBS Workflow

4.1 Background

Whole genome bisulphite sequencing files are frequently generated with Illumina sequencing. The PryfynMeth pipeline can handle file types output from the Bismark Bisulfite Read Mapper and Methylation Caller pipeline. This section discusses destranded methylation data. Destranded data merges strands. For CpGs, destranding might be preferable, especially with low coverage.

- Stranded data has the + and - strands as separate entities.
- Destranded data merges strands. For CpGs, destranding might be preferable, especially with low coverage.

Example: Stranded vs Destranded

Table 5: Example methylation entries

Chr	Start	Strand	Methylation Fraction	Type
Chr1	101	+	8/9	Stranded
Chr1	102	-	11/15	Stranded
Chr1	101	*	19/24	Destranded

If filtering on coverage (e.g., coverage ≥ 10), you may discard useful strand data (e.g., 8/9 becomes 0/0). Destranding helps preserve meaningful information in such cases. Stranded data can be generated using Bismark's `bismark_methylation_extractor` command in the pipeline illustrated below.

4.2 Generating Stranded Methylation Data

4.2.1 Alignment

```
Bismark-0.24.2/bismark \  
  --multicore 4 --genome dir_to_genome_files -1 {input.read1} -2 {  
  input.read2}
```

Be sure to also align to lambda to generate values for your metadata table.

4.2.2 Remove PCR duplicates

```
Bismark-0.24.2/deduplicate_bismark -p --bam {input}
```

4.2.3 Extract Methylation

```
Bismark-0.24.2/bismark_methylation_extractor \  
  --no_overlap --comprehensive --bedgraph --report --  
  cytosine_report \  
  --genome_folder dir_to_genome_files {input}
```

4.2.4 Generate Coverage File

```
Bismark-0.24.2/coverage2cytosine \  
  -o {params} --merge_CpG \  
  --genome_folder dir_to_genome_files {input}
```

4.3 Stranded WGBS Preprocessing

Once you have generated cov output files from Bismark's coverage2cytosine command, the output cov files are used in PryfynMeth's Preprocessing step.

```
python pryfynmeth/bisulphite_preprocessing.py -i Input -o all_Input -type  
  destrand --output_type all, coverage or shared #OPTION_DEPENDENT:  
  template_cov_file.cov
```

- -i — Input folder: cov or report files.
- -o — Output folder: reformatted files to be used by binomial.py.
- -type — stranded or destrand.
- -output_type — One of: all, coverage, or shared.

The following will retain every row that has coverage in at least 1 sample for stranded methylation data. This approach will ensure each sample is treated the same in FDR, but will minimise the number of rows (potentially not by much):

```
python pryfynmeth/bisulphite_preprocessing.py -i Input -o all_Input -type  
  destrand --output_type shared
```

The following will only keep rows with coverage in each individual sample. This approach will result in each sample being treated differently with FDR, but will reduce the number of tests:

```
python pryfynmeth/bisulphite_preprocessing.py -i Input -o all_Input -type  
  destrand --output_type coverage
```

To get an output which has the methylation status for every site of stranded data, you will first need to generate a template cov file for each row. To generate the template cov file, you will need to rerun coverage2cytosine, artificially creating coverage at each genomic CpG. Take any of your CpG report.txt files and run this:

```
awk '$6 == "CG" { print $1, $2, $3, 10, 10, $6, $7 }' OFS="\t" file.
CpG_report.txt > fake_CpG_report.txt

/Bismark-0.24.2/coverage2cytosine \
-o master_cpg.cov --merge_CpGs \
--genome_folder /path_to_genome/ fake_CpG_report.txt

cut -f1-3 master_cpg.cov.CpG_report.merged_CpG_evidence.cov >
template_cov_file.cov
```

Then you can run the following to retain every row for stranded methylation data. This approach will ensure each sample is treated the same in FDR. Note that a template cov file is needed to be added:

```
python pryfynmeth/bisulphite_preprocessing.py -i Input -o all_Input -type
destranded --output_type all template_cov_file.cov
```

4.4 Binomial Test

To determine whether an individual site is methylated in whole genome methylation sequencing, it's common practice to assess if the observed methylation level is significantly higher than what would be expected by chance. This is typically done by comparing the observed methylation proportion to a statistical threshold, often using a binomial test. In whole genome bisulphite sequencing and Nanopore sequencing, this threshold is determined by the percentage methylation found in lambda spiked DNA. To identify methylated sites, you can use the binomial.py command.

This is perhaps the most important part of this pipeline. This uses the same input command for all file types. The metadata false discovery rate (lambda) can be determined by aligning the reads to a lambda genome and determining the percentage of calls that are read as methylated. Your input directory for destranded data are output files from bismark_methylation_extractor with the `-merge_cpg` flag (ends in *.cov).

```
python pryfynmeth/binomial.py -meta metadata.txt -platform illu -i
Input_dir -o Binomial_output
```

- `-meta` — An input metadata file that reads the fail rate of calling methylation. An example metadata file can be found [here](#)
- `-platform` — nano for Nanopore, illu for Illumina (WGBS)

-
- -i — Input file. This is created either from the Nanopore or Bisulphite pipelines outlined above
 - -o — Output Directory to be created shared.

4.5 Filtering

Once you have generated binomial results, you may wish to filter samples with low read count. The `filter.py` command does just that. By setting a threshold it will output three folders. The first will be a full list of your sites in your binomial test output, but with the values and statistics adjusted considering your filtering. The second will be a folder of each sample's methylated sites (sites with FDR less than 0.05). The final, will scan each of your methylated site files, and will add genomic locations that have been excluded from other samples, making sure each sample has the same number of input site.

```
python pryfynmeth/filter.py -i Binomial_Results_Folder -f
output_adjusted_sites -m output_pass_binomial -s output_shared_sites
-threshold 10 -r reverted_folder
```

- -i An input folder which should be the output (-o) from the binomial step
- -f An output folder that will give a full list of sites, but with adjusted values. For example, if threshold is set at 10 and the site in question passes FDR but has fewer reads than 10, the reads, methylation count and non-methylation count will be set at 0, and the FDR will become 1 (failing).
- -m An output folder that subsets each input file to only give methylated sites (ie those with an FDR less than 0.05).
- -threshold Anything lower than the number set here will convert the methylation count, non-methylation count and coverage numbers to 0, making the FDR fail.
- -s An output folder that subsets the input files, so that only rows that are methylated in at least one sample are kept.
- -r This is an optional tag (but recommended). If included, sites which failed binomial but have over the threshold coverage will be reverted to their original input values. The logic for this is that by changing these values to 0, you may artificially be increasing the difference between samples and consequentially increase the number of differentially methylated sites. This example has threshold set at 10:

I find it easiest to run all options (filtered, methylated, subset and revert), which allows you to inspect how many sites proceed for each option, before making a decision for the next step.

Table 6: Comparison of results with default and `-revert` options

Input	Default	-revert
1 / 9 (fail FDR)	0/0	0/0
1 / 20 (fail FDR)	0/0	1/20
2 / 20 (pass FDR)	2/20	2/20

5 Format for Differential Methylation Analyses

An important part of studying methylomics is determining differing levels of methylation between conditions. For this, you would need to perform a differential methylation analysis. Here we provide scripts to format the data generated by PryfynMeth for such analyses:

5.1 DSS

For use with DSS, you can use the

dss_prepare.py command *oneither your binomial, filtered, methylated or shared folders* :

```
python pryfynmeth/dss_prepare.py -i output_shared_sites -o DSS_folder
```

- -i An input folder with the desired files to be used for DSS (eg. -f, -m or -s output from filter.py)
- -o An output folder for files in the DSS input format

6 PCA

To generate a PCA of your outputs, you can run the following command:

```
python pca.py \  
-i Input_Folder \  
--scale \  
--min-samples 3 \  
--impute median \  
--metadata metadata.txt \  
--label-fontsize 12 \  
--axis-fontsize 14
```

- -i - Input folder with txt files (eg. Input for your Differential Methylation)
- -scale -
- -min-samples - The minimum number of samples required for a specific site for it to be included in the PCA. The more sites the more robust, but too many samples may greatly reduce the number of sites that contribute to the PCA. A good number is around 70
- -metadata - metadata file (example here)
- -impute - How to incorporate the sites which have no coverage. mean / median would take the average from all samples.
- -label-fontsize - Size for your sample labels
- -axis-fontsize - Size for your axis labels

7 Statistics

To obtain the percentage of methylated sites, level of methylation and the coverage, you can use `statistics.py`. The input folder (-i) can be your binomial test results, your filtered results, methylated sites results or shared CpG results (although the latter 2 won't give you measures as to how much of the unmethylated genome you're missing).

```
python3 pryfynmeth/statistics.py -i input_folder
```